

№3

2023 | МАЙ

ЗАМОНАВИЙ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР АХБОРОТНОМАСИ

НАУЧНЫЙ ВЕСТНИК
SCIENTIFIC BULLETIN

ISSN: 2181-4554
DOI Journal 10.56017/2181-4554

ВЕСТНИК СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ

ТОМ-I, НОМЕР-3

**ЗАМОНАВИЙ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР
АХБОРОТНОМАСИ**

I-ЖИЛД, 3-СОН

BULLETIN OF CONTEMPORARY STUDIES

VOLUME-I, ISSUE-3

ТОШКЕНТ – 2023

Бош муҳаррир:

Бахриддинов О. – юридик фанлар номзоди, доцент

Масъул муҳаррир:

Ахмедов Р. – социология фанлари бўйича фалсафа доктори

Таҳририят аъзолари:

Эгамбердиева А. – психология фанлари номзоди, доценти
Мирзабеков Ғ. – педагогика фанлари номзоди, доценти
Гафуров У. – иқтисод фанлари доктори, профессор
Насиров Р. – тарих фанлари доктори, профессори
Фозилов У. – юридик фанлар номзоди, доцент
Пўлатова Д. – фалсафа фанлари номзоди, доцент
Якубов И. – сиёсий фанлар номзоди, доцент
Азизов У. – социология фанлари бўйича фалсафа доктори
Матчанов А. – биология фанлари доктори, профессор
Зайтов А. – физика-математика фанлари доктори, профессор
Гафурова Д. – кимё фанлар доктори, доцент
Касимов И. – тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор
Марипова С. – геология-минерология фанлари номзоди
Каримова С. – фармацевтика фанлари номзоди, доцент
Матёқубова Т. – филология фанлари номзоди, доцент
Қодирова С. – санъатшунослик фанлари доктори, профессор
Сатторов З. – техника фанлари номзоди, профессор
Шодманов М. – қишлоқ хўжалиги фанлари номзоди, доцент
Сафарова Н. – география фанлари номзоди, доцент
Мустаев Б. – архитектура фанлари бўйича фалсафа доктори
Якубжонова Ш. – география фанлари бўйича фалсафа доктори

Мазкур илмий-амалий ва таҳлилий-қийосий ахборотнома Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президенти Администрацияси ҳузуридаги Ахборот ва оммавий коммуникациялар агентлиги томонидан 2023 йил 24 февраль куни № 065358-сонли гувоҳнома билан оммавий ахборот воситаси сифатида давлат рўйхатидан ўтказилган.

Page Maker\Верстка\Саҳифаловчи: Абдураҳмон Хасанов

Таҳририят манзили: <https://imfaktor.uz>, 100152, Тошкент шаҳри, Учтепа тумани, “Ватан” МФЙ, Чилонзор 24-мавзеси, 2/27-уй.

Телефон номер: +99894-410 11 55, E-mail: tahririyat@imfaktor.uz

© IMFAKTOR Pages, 2023 йил.

© Муаллифлар жамоаси, 2023 йил.

ЗАМОНАВИЙ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР АХБОРОТНОМАСИ

ВЕСТНИК СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ | BULLETIN OF CONTEMPORARY STUDIES

Санъатишунослик фанлари

ABDURAHMANOV Ibrohim

Candidate of Arts (PDh), Associate Professor

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7895684>

HEAVENLY SYMBOLS OF RARE DEVONBEGI MADRAS DECORATION

ANNOTATION

The article summarizes the information about the symbolic nature of the majolica on the facade of the Nadir Devan Begi madrasa, built during the reign of the ruler of Bukhara, Imam Quli.

Keywords. Majolica, architectural decoration, mosque, workshop, astrology, heraldry, cosmogony.

NOYOB DEVONBEGING SAMOVIY RAMZLARI MADRAS BEZAKLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Maqolada Buxoro hukmdori Imom Quli davrida qurilgan Nodir Devan Begi madrasasi fasadidagi majolikaning ramziy tabiati haqidagi ma'lumotlar jamlangan.

Kalit so'zlar: Majolika, me'moriy bezak, masjid, ustaxona, astrologiya, geraldika, kosmogoniya.

НЕБЕСНЫЕ СИМВОЛЫ РЕДКОГО ДЕВОНБЕГИ УКРАШЕНИЕ МАДРАСА

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье обобщена информация о символическом характере майолики на фасаде медресе Надир Деван Беги, построенного во времена правления правителя Бухары Имама Кули.

Ключевые слова: Майолика, архитектурное убранство, мечеть, мастерская, астрология, геральдика, космогония.

Enter. Bukhara flourished as the pride of the country during the reign of Imam Kuli Khan. The development of many areas of artistic culture is taken seriously. In the capital city and its surroundings, conditions are created for the development of local handicrafts, many workshops operate. Strong swords, knives, shields and helmets are made by local craftsmen, studded with rare stones, covered with colored metals.

Bukhara weapons are extremely durable, strong and easy to use, so they are popular around the world. As a result, the fame of Imamquli Khan's kingdom will be greatly improved.

The main part. Special attention is paid to the development of the field of architecture. The ruler's minister, Nadirmirza Togay ibn Sultan, is involved in creative work in this regard. The Madrasa of Nadir Devonbegi, built under his direct leadership in 1622-1623, continues to amaze tourists from all over the world with its magnificence and applied pictorial decorations. On the facade of the entrance gate of the building, a pair of fairy-tale birds flying into the sky is expressed in a deeply dynamic state. It is noted in the sources that this mythological supernatural creature is described as having the head of a rooster, the neck of a snake, and the chest of a swallow. There are various myths and legends about the history of the construction of the monument. One of them has such information. Nadir Devonbegi, the minister of financial affairs in the palace of Imam Quli Khan (1611-1642), made a great contribution to further increase the reputation of Bukhara as a place where science and art developed. In the sources, it is recorded that for more than two years, he taught them about knowledge at the suggestion of the Indians. On his way back, the Indian ruler presented him with two precious jeweled lamps as a gift. On the way, the minister stops in Afghanistan and rests for a day. A precious jeweled lamp charms the Afghan king. When Nodirbekka offers to sell this rare stone, he does not agree.

The minister was welcomed with great ceremony in Bukhara and as a progressive, spiritual and spiritually perfect person of his time, he married the daughter of Imam Quli Khan, who had no equal in beauty. In the city of Bukhara, the capital city of Imam Quli Khan, serious attention is paid to the creation of a completely new image of mosque-madrasas. In this process, Nadir Devonbegi had a great position as the patron and creator of all good deeds. However, for years she was plagued by childlessness. He often spent nights awake, wondering what to do. One of these days, an idea comes to his mind. That is, he decides to spend all his wealth on the path of goodness. In particular, he sells a precious jewel given to him by an Indian ruler and begins to make a plan to build a magnificent madrasa.

Early in the morning, he leaves for Afghanistan with a large caravan. The Afghan king welcomes the guests with joy. The minister sells him a lamp with a rare gem. In exchange for a priceless stone, the Afghan king gives him a large amount of gold. He loaded gold and other precious wealth on a caravan of camels and returned to his homeland. When Nodirbek arrived in Bukhara, the next day, he gathered the famous master-architects of his time and ordered to build an architectural ensemble in front of the Kokaldosh madrasa, a pool, a house and a madrasa that complement each other. The work will be started soon. In 1623, the construction of the madrasa was completed. The pond in the square stood out in the city in terms of its majesty, appearance and shape. All the buildings around the square are united and brought to a unified architectural solution.

The majestic walls in front of the madrasa are decorated separately. At the top and sides of the huge gate at the entrance, a couple of amulet-like decorations are worked on the top of the arch. The paintings skillfully depict a pair of legendary Humo birds chasing two suns with the help of exquisite mosaics by the masters. According to S. Bulatov, the white and black circle and circle-shaped images on the body of the Humo bird refer to the heavenly planets. The 18 figures in the image are a symbolic representation of the 18 thousand bright worlds. The fact that the bird's tail is drawn in a wavy form is directly compared to the unevenness of the human life path. The green color in it indicates goodness, and the black line seems to contain the symbols of evil. The fact that the wings of the huma are white directly indicates that the intention of our people is purity, peace and tranquility.

The overall composition of the mural depicts the legendary Humo bird carrying a white pig on its feet. All tiled decorations are reflected in bright colors. In local folkloric traditions, the pig has long been interpreted as an unclean morsel. Local masters paid attention to the semantic and mythological roots of each ornament they depicted. According to the Chinese astrological calendar, the twelfth month is called the pig.

He is a giver of difficult moments and can be an example to others by working diligently throughout the year and fighting for his own happiness. They keep all the bad luck away and look to the future with hope. Various disappointments and problems will recede from such people, it is predicted that they will open the door to opportunities for luck, material wealth and success. The Year of the Pig will be sufficiently peaceful and tolerant. Because this animal, with its benevolence and justice, is able to make a sharp turn not only at the state level, but also in the life of every person. In the year of the pig, financial affairs will be effective, but the "owner" of the year will help to strengthen health and give strength and cheerful spirit. At the same time, he lives in a cheerful mood, striving to make his dreams come true through bold action. Most of all, this predatory creature hates lies, it can throw and dismember opponents and ill-wishers in all directions with a flick of the wrist. But his extreme care can be felt from the spring. Along with the March sun, material blessings begin to pour into people's lives. The Pig always strives to find unconventional solutions to problems. Therefore, it is predicted that creative people and creative thinkers will easily reach the top of fame. It is closer to the truth that master painters and architects sought this essence from this image. In fact, in this bright world, every living being comes into the world with its own sustenance.

Earning one's sustenance through honest work has been the life philosophy and eternal dream of every Muslim believer. It is not for nothing that the image of the sun, representing the level of perfection in the form of a human face, is depicted in the middle part of the top of the peshtok. It is closer to the truth that the image depicted in the Sun, the highest peak of spiritual purity, is consecrated as a symbol of warmth, tenderness, light life.

First of all, local masters attached great importance to the interpretation of the legendary image of a bird in folk poetry as a symbolic expression of age-old dreams of flying in the sky and bringing a distant destination closer. In Uzbek folk tales, it is based on the embodiment of a fantastic bird as a friend, protector, companion of a positive hero, who takes him out of the "seven darknesses". In Turkic peoples, this divine creature has Humo, Anko, state bird, happiness bird, Marqumomo, Kuntubulgan, Bulbuligoya and other variants.

This image was taken from the plots of "Kahramon", "Oynai Jahonnamo", "Rustam", "Kenja Batir" and a number of other fairy tales. Through this image, great attention is paid to the peace, tranquility and well-being of our people. From time immemorial, the image of Khumo, a symbol of good fortune, has been used by masters in the art of painting, jewelry, jewelry, goldsmithing, embroidery, pottery and carving, sometimes as an ornament, sometimes as a talisman.

Summary. However, the symmetrical arrangement of architectural monuments means that people's desires and opportunities are in harmony in their lives. The expressiveness of the drawings in the pictures is also typical for the traditional plot. A distinctive feature of Bukhara wall paintings and drawings is that, although they have retained a connection with astral themes, not astronomical or heraldic (although these moments are present in them), they primarily embody pictorial folklore. It expresses the general nature of art in relation to folklore traditions.

ИҚТИБОСЛАР/СНОСКИ/REFERENCES

1. Булатов С.С, Соипова М.С. Бадий таҳлил тамойиллари. –(тасвирий, амалий ва меъморчилик санъат асарлари мисолида). -Монография. Тошкент: Фан ва технологиялар маркази, 2016. –Б.208.
2. Ремпель Л.И. Историко-художественные заметки. -//в книге «Вопросы изобразительного искусства Узбекистана». Ташкент: Издательства имени Г.Гуляма, 1973. – С.86.
4. Ҳакимов А.А. Ўзбекистон санъати тарихи: қадимги давр, ўрта асрлар, ҳозирги замон. –Тошкент: Zilol buloq., 2022. –Б.200.
5. Руи Гонзалес де Клафихо. Самарқандга – Амир Темур саройига саёҳат кундалиги (1403-1406 йиллар). –Тошкент: Ўзбекистон, 2010. –Б.148-149.
6. Ibrohim Rahimovich Abdurahmonov. Concept of mythology represented in fine arts of Uzbekistan. -//Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research. Impact Factor: SJIF 2020=6.882. Voll 9, Issue 10, October, 2020. P.143-147.
7. Ibrokhim Rakhimovich Abdurakhmonov. Reflection Of Folklore in Applied Art Of Uzbekistan (From The Beginning Of The XX Century To The gos). The American Journal Of Social Science and Education Innovations (ISSN-2689-100X). February 27. 2021. P.166-171. [https://doi.org/10,37547](https://doi.org/10.37547). Impact Factor 202: 5.857.
8. Ibragim Abdurahmonov(2018). Reflektion of Written Dastans in Maveraunnahr Miniature (XIV-XVII Centuries).-//International journal of research. With Impact Factor 5.60. Dectmber. 2018. P.425-432.
9. Ibrakhim R. Abdurakhmonov. Interpretation of mythological topics in the fine art of the XX century. Art and design: social science, volume 02, issue 02, 2022 1 e-issn: 2181-2918; p-issn: 2181-290x.
10. Иброҳим Абдурахмонов. Ўзбекистон тасвирий санъатида фольклор мотивлари талқини. Academic Research in Educational Sciences VOLUME 2 | ISSUE 12 | 2021 ISSN: 2181-1385 Scientific Journal Impact Factor (SJIF) 2021: 11.723 Directory Indexing of International Research Journals-CiteFactor 2020-21: 0.89 DOI: 10.24412/2181-1385-2021-12-1323-1327.

ISSN: 2181-4554
DOI Journal 10.56017/2181-4554

ЗАМОНАВИЙ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР АХБОРОТНОМАСИ

Ї-ЖИЛД, 3-СОҢ

ВЕСТНИК СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ
ТОМ-Ї, НОМЕР-3

BULLETIN OF CONTEMPORARY STUDIES
VOLUME-Ї, ISSUE-3

“Замонавий тадқиқотлар ахборотномаси” электрон журнали 2023 йил 24 февраль куни № 065358-сонли гувоҳнома билан оммавий ахборот воситаси сифатида давлат рўйхатидан ўтказилган.

Муассис: «IMFAKTOR Pages» масъулияти чекланган жамияти.

Таҳририят манзили: 100152, Тошкент шаҳри, Учтепа тумани, “Ватан” МФЙ, Чилонзор 24-мавзеси, 2-уй.

Телефон номер: +99894-410 11 55

Эл. почта: tahririyat@imfaktor.uz

Веб-сайт: www.imfaktor.uz